

SELF MOTIVATION : DEVELOP & IMPROVE YOUR SELF

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Abstract

Motivation can be conceived of as a cycle in which thoughts influence behaviors, behaviors drive performance, performance impacts thoughts, and the cycle begins again. Each stage of the cycle is composed of many dimensions including attitudes, beliefs, intentions, effort, and withdrawal which can all affect the motivation that an individual experiences. Ability to do what needs to be done, without influence from other people or situations. People with self motivation can find a reason and strength to complete a task, even when challenging, without giving up or needing another to encourage them There are many advantages to self-motivation. People who are self-motivated, for example, tend to be more organised, have good time management skills and more self-esteem and confidence.

Key words : Reasons, Developing Factors, Problem & Needs.

MEANING OF MOTIVATION:

Motivation is what pushes us to achieve our goals, feel more fulfilled and improve overall quality of life. Daniel Goleman, the author of several seminal books on Emotional Intelligence, identified four elements that make up motivation:

- Personal drive to achieve, the desire to improve or to meet certain standards;
- Commitment to personal or organisational goals;
- Initiative, which he defined as ‘readiness to act on opportunities’; and
- Optimism, the ability to keep going and pursue goals in the face of setbacks.

DEFINITION SELF MOTIVATION:

Staying motivated is a struggle — our drive is constantly assaulted by negative thoughts and anxiety about the future. Everyone faces doubt and depression. What separates the highly successful is the ability to keep moving forward.

There is no simple solution for a lack of motivation. Even after beating it, the problem reappears at the first sign of failure. The key is understanding your thoughts and how they drive your emotions. By learning how to nurture motivating thoughts, neutralize negative ones, and focus on the task at hand, you can pull yourself out of a slump before it gains momentum.

THREE PRIMARY REASONS WE LOSE MOTIVATION:

There are 3 primary reasons we lose motivation.

1. **Lack of confidence** – If you don't believe you can succeed, what's the point in trying?
2. **Lack of focus** – If you don't know what you want, do you really want anything?
3. **Lack of direction** – If you don't know what to do, how can you be motivated to do it?

HOW TO BOOST CONFIDENCE:

The first motivation killer is a lack of confidence. When this happens to me, it's usually because I'm focusing entirely on what I want and neglecting what I already have. When you only think about what you want, your mind creates explanations for why you aren't getting it. This creates negative thoughts. Past failures, bad breaks, and personal weaknesses dominate your mind. You become jealous of your competitors and start making excuses for why you can't succeed. In this state, you tend to make a bad impression, assume the worst about others, and lose self confidence.

The way to get out of this thought pattern is to focus on gratitude. Set aside time to focus on everything positive in your life. Make a mental list of your strengths, past successes, and current advantages. We tend to take our strengths for granted and dwell on our failures. By making an effort to feel grateful, you'll realize how competent and successful you already are. This will rejuvenate your confidence and get you motivated to build on your current success.

It might sound strange that repeating things you already know can improve your mindset, but it's amazingly effective. The mind distorts reality to confirm what it wants to believe. The more negatively you think, the more examples your mind will discover to confirm that belief. When

you truly believe that you deserve success, your mind will generate ways to achieve it. The best way to bring success to yourself is to genuinely desire to create value for the rest of the world.

DEVELOPING FACTORS:

A. TANGIBLE FOCUS:

The second motivation killer is a lack of focus. How often do you focus on what you don't want, rather than on a concrete goal? We normally think in terms of fear. I'm afraid of being poor. I'm afraid no one will respect me. I'm afraid of being alone. The problem with this type of thinking is that fear alone isn't actionable. Instead of doing something about our fear, it feeds on itself and drains our motivation.

If you're caught up in fear based thinking, the first step is focusing that energy on a well defined goal. By defining a goal, you automatically define a set of actions. If you have a fear of poverty, create a plan to increase your income. It could be going back to school, obtaining a higher paying job, or developing a profitable website. The key is moving from an intangible desire to concrete, measurable steps.

By focusing your mind on a positive goal instead of an ambiguous fear, you put your brain to work. It instantly begins devising a plan for success. Instead of worrying about the future you start to do something about it. This is the first step in motivating yourself to take action. When know what you want, you become motivated to take action.

B. DIRECTION:

The final piece in the motivational puzzle is direction. If focus means having an ultimate goal, direction is having a day-to-day strategy to achieve it. A lack of direction kills motivation because without an obvious next action we succumb to procrastination. An example of this is a person who wants to have a popular blog, but who spends more time reading posts about blogging than actually writing articles.

The key to finding direction is identifying the activities that lead to success. For every goal, there are activities that pay off and those that don't. Make a list of all your activities and arrange them based on results. Then make a make an action plan that focuses on the activities

that lead to big returns. To continue the example from above, a blogger's list would look something like this:

1. Write content
2. Research relevant topics
3. Network with other bloggers
4. Optimize design and ad placements
5. Answer comments and email
6. Read other blogs

SELF MOTIVATION –IMPROVE YOUR SELF:

This is central to everything positive that you want to do in your life. Perhaps it is even more important than your self esteem! What you say to yourself is extremely important and if you want to learn more about self talk and how to help yourself by talking to yourself more positively visit the self talk page now.

If you want to improve your motivation or self esteem or improve yourself in any way you need the desire and will to do it. I hear you saying that not everything comes from within. You may be motivated by external factors, others may encourage you to start something new or begin moving in a positive direction. You can be motivated by faith, by your belief in God and in doing what is right. You can even be motivated by negative events to achieve positively. But what is important is how you think about what happens to you. Optimism is a great help and will prepare you for new challenges and make it more likely that you will succeed. Negative thinking will always demotivate you so you need to think positively even in the most difficult situations. This is not denial of reality but a useful tool in your armour. Read how you can end negative thoughts and motivate yourself more.

NEED SELF MOTIVATION:

- You cannot always rely on others to encourage you, if you have positive friends who are always there when you need them then you are indeed lucky and very much in the minority. If you are lonely or have few friends when you face any difficulties in your life you must rely on your own motivation to get you through. Lack of self motivation at that time could lead to depression.

- You need self motivation to achieve because if you don't encourage yourself to accept opportunity and challenge who will?
- To plan and find direction in your life
- To take up a new activity, hobby or challenge
- To be enthusiastic about life and living
- To have the courage to see things through despite setbacks or negative comments from others

PROBLEM WITH YOUR MOTIVATION:

Even the most positive of people sometimes face a situation where they lack motivation. This happens to us all because we all face the same or at least similar difficulties in life. True you may be affected more or less than others because you react differently to the challenges and setbacks which you face. It is your attitude and responses to life which dictate how you feel.

Abusive people lower your self esteem and put you down. If you live with an abusive person you are at a big disadvantage and may suffer very low confidence. The best advice is to get this abusive person out of your life, don't accept abuse ever. If you absolutely can't escape that person then you need great inner strength to stand up to it.

Self hypnosis is a wonderful way to improve your self motivation. Try this amazing self hypnosis download – Building your self esteem now! It really works!

You may have friends who are negative or who put you down. This shows they have a problem but the tragedy is these people suck you dry of positive energy and being with negative people can only sap your inner strengths. Chances are that any self motivation you have they will slowly destroy and bring you down to their level.

SOME SUGGESTIONS:

- Focus on what you really enjoy doing, maybe on something you want to take up or on a hobby you've always wanted to devote more time to. What's stopping you? Think about giving it priority to start doing what you love doing.
- Make a list of things you'd like to improve on and how you're going to do it

- Review all the successes you've enjoyed in every area of your life, totally forget any negatives, just positive successes here!
- Start an exercise program – force yourself to do it, it'll make you feel much more positive.
- Contact a positive friend and have a chat.
- Read inspiring books that will help heal your mind and improve your attitude. I have put together a list of highly recommended self help books I know will help you so take a look and order one or two – you're going to find inspiration on every page!

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